

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF ELECTRIC FIELD TECHNOLOGY ON QUALITY AND NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF JUICES. A REVIEW

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Abstract

Heat treatment, freezing, aseptic packaging and treatment with antimicrobial agents are the main methods of preserving food products. At the same time, the methods of preservation used can have a negative impact on the quality of plant materials and juice products. Therefore, scientists are constantly searching for and developing new technologies for processing raw materials that can ensure not only the safety of products, but also preserve their quality and nutritional value as much as possible. Juices offer a convenient means of consuming bioactive compounds and essential nutrients that are critical for human health. However, traditional thermal processing used in juice and beverage production to inactivate spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms as well as endogenous enzymes can lead to degradation of bioactive compounds and vitamins. In response, non-thermal technologies have emerged as a promising alternative to traditional thermal processing, with pulsed electric field (PEF) technology emerging as an innovative and sustainable choice. This article reviews scientific publications that have investigated the effects of PEF on the microbiological, physicochemical, functional, nutritional and sensory qualities of vegetable and fruit juices. The review found that PEF induces electroporation phenomena in cell membranes, resulting in reversible or irreversible changes. Therefore, a detailed investigation of the effects of PEF process variables on juice properties is essential. Monitoring factors such as electric field strength, frequency, pulse width, total processing time and specific energy are important to ensure the production of a safe and chemically/kinetically stable product. PEF technology has proven its effectiveness in microbiological and enzymatic inactivation in vegetable and fruit juices, mitigating factors that contribute to quality deterioration while maintaining the physicochemical characteristics of these products. In addition, PEF processing does not compromise the content of substances with functional, nutritional and sensory properties such as phenolic compounds and vitamins. Compared with alternative processing methods such as mild thermal processing and other non-thermal technologies, PEF processing consistently shows comparable results in terms of physicochemical properties, functional properties, nutritional quality and overall safety. However, future research is needed on the application of PEF technology. Issues related to microbial and enzymatic inactivation, production of intracellular compounds and other aspects need to be addressed.

Keywords: juice, fruits, electroporation, microbial inactivation, phenolic compounds, anthocyanins, antioxidant activity.

Introduction

One of the main challenges facing the food industry today is to ensure the quality of food products. The absence of spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms in food products is usually ensured by adding both various preservatives and antimicrobial agents. Therefore, to provide natural products that do not contain preservatives, the food industry is constantly looking for alternative methods of processing food products that meet consumer requirements [1]. Over the past decade, considerable attention has been paid to products with preventive and functional properties that promote health. Consequently, consumer preferences will be in favor of minimally processed foods with high-quality organoleptic indicators and high nutritional value [2]. Food industry enterprises should be focused on the production of such products, using modern processing methods that allow maximal preservation of quality indicators, be safe and have antioxidant activity. In this regard, non-thermal technologies for the processing of food and beverages are considered as an alternative to thermal processes [3-4]. These innovative technologies are based on principles that help ensure the microbiological stability of products, maximum preservation of the physicochemical properties, organoleptic indicators

and nutritional value of food products. In addition, the role of these technologies in preserving the environment is noted, the implementation of non-thermal technologies in the production of food and beverages represents a contribution to the sustainable development of the manufacturing sector. Conventional thermal processes contribute to global warming primarily due to the emission of greenhouse gases, especially CO₂. Because fossil fuels such as coal, oil and natural gas are burned to produce thermal energy in industrial processes or electricity generation, they release large amounts of CO₂ into the atmosphere. This process significantly increases the concentration of greenhouse gases that trap heat and contribute to the greenhouse effect. On the other hand, non-thermal technologies allow the use of sustainable energy sources such as wind, sun, biogas, and others. Modern non-thermal technologies being developed and proposed for industrial implementation in the food industry are pulsed electric field (PEF), high intensity ultrasound (HIUS), high hydrostatic pressure (HPP) processing, supercritical carbon dioxide, and others [5,6]. Drinking juice provides the body with nutrients, vitamins, antioxidants, dietary fiber and phytochemicals contained in vegetables and fruits. The influence of thermal processes during the

processing of vegetables and fruits into juice products leads to a partial loss of nutrients and biologically active compounds. Therefore, the development and implementation of modern non-thermal sterilization processes that contribute to the maximum preservation of the properties of freshly squeezed juice is an effective strategy to produce safe juice products of high quality and nutritional value [7,8].

PEF is an innovative technology based on non-thermal processes that involves the use of electrical pulses to treat food products. During the process, electrical current is applied at short intervals, causing changes in the microstructure of food by redistributing charged particles in cellular structures and macromolecules [9,10]. These changes lead to microbial and enzymatic inactivation, ensuring microbiological safety and kinetic stability of the beverage. In addition, PEF technology has various applications, such as the extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials and food waste, molecular complexation, modification of biopolymers, as well as pre-treatment before freezing/thawing and drying processes, etc [11-13]. The effect of pulsed electric field helps to preserve nutritional and functional products without compromising sensory characteristics. Recent studies in the literature indicate that PEF is a promising technology for non-thermal processing of fruit and vegetable juices. Studies on PEF processing on the nutritional safety, functional, and sensory parameters of vegetable and fruit juices can be found in the literature [14-18]. Innovative processing technologies such as PEF are being assessed due to the high demand for the process that primarily preserve the health-beneficial and sensory properties of juices. In this context, this review discussed the impacts of PEF technology on vegetable and fruit juices processing. Challenges and opportunities of implementing this non-thermal process in juice production were examined, reviewing the impacts of the electric field on physico-chemical, microbiological, nutritional, functional, and sensory characteristics. Additionally, aspects related to the severity level of PEF treatments were discussed/

1. Basics of PEF technology.

PEF is a non-thermal technology that causes the formation of pores in the cell membrane. This phenomenon is called electroporation. The application of an electric field generates charges in the membrane components. Charges of opposite polarity attract each other, and charges of the same polarity repel each other. This creates spaces in the cell membrane called pores [18]. The intensity of the applied PEF determines whether the pore formation will be reversible or irreversible. Reversible electroporation occurs when the pore exists only during the application of the electric field. Consequently, after the application, the membrane returns to its original conformation. However, irreversible electroporation, also referred to as permanent, happens when the membrane is ruptured due to the application of the PEF shows reversible and irreversible electroporation. Electroporation depends on the size, type and shape of the cell, membrane characteristics, process conditions, among other factors. In general, the presence of pores increases cell permeability through the

membrane, therefore, obtaining intracellular compounds present in the plasma is possible. Furthermore, electroporation compromises cellular integrity, resulting in alterations in enzymes and proteins, culminating in microbial inactivation [6,9,18].

The PEF treatment involves the application of high-voltage electric current (10–80 kV/cm) in short-duration intervals known as pulses, lasting approximately from microseconds to nanoseconds [8,9,18]. Thus, the efficiency of the treatments of this innovative technology in food and beverage quality depends on the process conditions, such as field strength (10–80 kV/cm), pulse width (0.2–80 μ s) and frequency (1–1500 Hz), treatment time (100–800 μ s), membrane polarity, electrodes used, food matrix, sample conductivity, among others shows the PEF application modes in a continuous and batch system [18].

During treatment with the electric field, the product can heat up [19]. This phenomenon is a consequence of the Joule effect, in which heat is generated when an electric current passes through a conductor applied PEF (35 kV/cm, treatment time 27 μ s, 155 Hz, 14 pulses) to strawberry juice and observed a temperature increase from 22.7 to 46.0 °C. Applied PEF (20 to 40 kV/cm, 10 to 50 pulses, pulse width 10 μ s, 1 Hz) with different field strengths and number of pulses to orange juice initially at 25.0 °C and, after treatment, the temperature ranged from 26.1 to 43.6 °C. For this reason, temperature monitoring and control measures such as the use of cooling baths are recommended so that PEF treatment can truly be classified as a nonthermal treatment [19-20]. Among emerging technologies, PEF and OH are techniques that involve the application of electric current through two electrodes in a known mass or food product to alter characteristics, achieve microbial and enzymatic inactivation, among other consequences. The differentiation between the two techniques lies in the mode of applying electric current occurs in short intervals in PEF treatment, as mentioned earlier, in the form of pulses. On the other hand, OH is a technique that aims to heat the sample through the Joule effect, which results from the passage of electric current through the material or conductive medium. During ohmic treatment, there are effects due to sample heating and nonthermal effects related to the passage of electric current through the medium, such as electroporation, for example. The sample heating promotes the inactivation of enzymes and deteriorating microorganisms, elimination of pathogens, and other changes. For the application of PEF and OH, it is necessary to have some equipment such as electric field generators, electrodes, pumps in the case of continuous systems, among others. Specifically in the case of PEF, the presence of an oscilloscope and field controller is extremely necessary to monitor the application of the electric field in the form of pulses, i.e., discontinuously. On the other hand, during OH application, the most essential equipment includes the power supply for electric current, the pair of electrodes, and the treatment chamber. In PEF processing, the process variables are field strength, frequency, pulse width, total treatment duration. In contrast, OH presents the electrical conductivity of the

sample, frequency and waveform, heat capacity, and electrode configuration as process variables [19,21].

2. Effects of PEF on microbiological quality.

PEF technology has been investigated as an alternative for quality control and microbiological safety in the juice and plant-based beverage industry. The exploration of non-thermal processing alternatives aims primarily at preserving the sensory and nutritional characteristics of the products [22]. Therefore, PEF technology has been studied as an alternative to conventional pasteurization and sterilization treatments. The mechanism of microbial inactivation associated with PEF is not completely elucidated, however the phenomenon of electroporation that occurs in membranes is the most widely accepted cause of cell death in microorganisms. The electropermeabilization of cell membranes in bacteria, fungi, yeast, among others, caused by high-voltage pulses, can lead to various effects ranging from mass transfer, such as water exudation and intracellular compound diffusion, to impairment of cellular functions, cell lysis, consequently resulting in cell death investigated the inactivation of *Staphylococcus aureus* and the release of metal ions from the cells after applying PEF (18.0 and 25.0 kV/cm, 0.5 Hz, pulse width 4 μ s, 2.59 and 5.00 kJ/kg) authors observed inactivation ranging between 1.0 and 3.5 logarithmic cycles of *Staphylococcus aureus* and the release of 98% and 15% of potassium and magnesium ions, respectively, which constitute the cell. Factors intrinsic to microbial cultures determine the effectiveness of PEF treatment, including the size and geometric shape of the cells, presentation (sporulated or vegetative form), type of microorganism, characteristics of the cell membrane, cultivation conditions, phase of microbial growth, presence of toxic substances in the medium, among other factors. In this context, bacteria are more resistant to PEF than molds and yeasts due to their smaller cell size. A cell has an irregular distribution of positive and negative charges on both sides of the membrane, resulting in a difference in electrical potential across the cell membrane, which is called transmembrane potential. When the electric field is applied, the ions are reorganized along the cell membrane, promoting changes in the electrical potential differential. This change in electrical potential is called induced transmembrane voltage (ITV), which, when it reaches a certain level of potential difference, results in the phenomenon of electroporation. The ITV is directly proportional to the applied electric field strength and the cell's radius. In this context, two cells with different radius require different electric field intensities to reach the same ITV. Consequently, the cell with a larger radius will require a less intense electric field compared to the smaller cell. Another very important point is that the extracellular and intracellular media are electrically conductive, while the cell membrane has a region exposed to conductive media and another insulating region, thus, areas exposed to environments with electrical conductors are more susceptible to electroporation. In this context, the larger the area exposed to extracellular and intracellular media, the more sensitive it is to electroporation. In addition, bacteria have a peptidoglycan layer which makes the structure of the cell membrane more rigid.

Bacterial spores, on the other hand, are resistant to treatment because the structure of the envelope prevents electroporation. Regarding shape, non-spherical microorganisms tend to be more resistant to PEF, once cell orientation during field application influences the effectiveness of the treatment. This resistance is attributed to some types of bacteria, protozoa, among others. Growth Regarding phase, cultures in the exponential phase are more sensitive to PEF compared to the stationary phase. During the cell division process, the size of the cell and cell membrane increases, thus the lipid bilayer becomes more prone to electroporation. Furthermore, the presence of substances such as ethanol and acids can increase the effectiveness of the electric field, since electroporation, even if reversible, promotes mass transfer. Therefore, acids and other toxic substances diffuse into the intracellular environment and compromise cellular activities electrically conductive, while the cell membrane has a region exposed to conductive media and another insulating region, thus, areas exposed to environments with electrical conductors are more susceptible to electroporation. In this context, the larger the area exposed to extracellular and intracellular media, the more sensitive it is to electroporation. In addition, bacteria have a peptidoglycan layer which makes the structure of the cell membrane more rigid. Bacterial spores, on the other hand, are resistant to treatment because the structure of the envelope prevents electroporation. Regarding shape, non-spherical microorganisms tend to be more resistant to PEF, once cell orientation during field application influences the effectiveness of the treatment. This resistance is attributed to some types of bacteria, protozoa, among others. Growth Regarding phase, cultures in the exponential phase are more sensitive to PEF compared to the stationary phase. During the cell division process, the size of the cell and cell membrane increases, thus the lipid bilayer becomes more prone to electroporation. Furthermore, the presence of substances such as ethanol and acids can increase the effectiveness of the electric field, since electroporation, even if reversible, promotes mass transfer. Therefore, acids and other toxic substances diffuse into the intracellular environment and compromise cellular activities [22,23]. In some studies, the reduction in microbial load of molds and yeasts is greater than that of bacteria. The mechanisms behind the previously mentioned phenomenon are not specified by Yildiz et al. and Jin and Aboelhaggag [24]. However, Jin et al. correlate cell size with resistance to PEF, while Yildiz et al. justified this resistance based on the morphological characteristics of different cell types. In this case, they exemplified that larger cells of molds and yeasts are more easily permeabilized compared to smaller cells such as bacteria [25].

In other studies, the reduction in bacterial microbial load was greater than the reduction in molds and yeasts. The authors of the studies did not point out a justification for the greater reduction in the microbial load of bacteria compared to molds and yeasts. However, they proposed techniques and processes to extend the shelf life of beverages using PEF and explained the

effects of PEF on cell structures [9,26-27]. Delso, Berzosa, et al. discussed the phenomenon of electroporation in microorganisms, emphasizing the dependence of the local transmembrane voltage. The potential across the membrane generated by an external electric field depends on the size of the cell and the intensity of the field. The lower reduction in bacterial count is related to the sporulated form, as these are not affected by the PEF process. The authors found that PEF treatment (17.5 kV/cm, 16 pulses, 10 μ s, 75 Hz, 73.6 kJ/kg) in grape juice inactivated all the microorganisms evaluated (molds, yeasts and total aerobic bacteria) to below the detection limit, regardless of whether the grapes were treated with PEF or not. They attributed this result to the uniform distribution of the electric field, which is related to the use of electrodes configured in parallel. Furthermore, after PEF treatment, the samples were initially heated up to 65 ± 1 °C at 20 °C. Thus, a synergistic effect of the increase in temperature contributed to the degree of inactivation observed in the study [16].

Yildiz et al. [28]. compared the characteristics of strawberry juice processed by pasteurization (TT – 72 °C, 15 s), HIUS (55 °C, 24 kHz, 0.29 W/mL, 120 μ m, 3 min), HPP (300 MPa, 1 min), and PEF (35 kV/cm, 155 Hz, 2 μ s, 27 μ s). The process conditions for each technology were established based on the reduction of 5 log CFU/mL of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7. Thus, the reduction in *E. coli* microbial count was the criterion established for process equivalence. Considering the results of the microbial reduction in the total count of aerobic and mesophilic bacteria (TMAC) and molds and yeasts (MY), the thermal treatment applied to the strawberry juice was the most effective for microbiological control with log reduction of 1.71 and 1.80, respectively. Processing with HIUS and HPP showed the same reduction for MY (1.70 log reduction). However, HPP was more efficient in reducing TMAC (1.41 log reduction). Among all observed treatments, PEF reduced both MY and TMAC the least with 1.60 and 1.71 log reduction, respectively. But the difference in microbial reduction among different treatments was very small. Therefore, further studies using these technologies are necessary for a thorough more evaluation concerning the microbial reduction criterion. In summary, PEF treatment is a potential alternative for microbial inactivation in fruit and vegetable juices since this technology has shown substantial reductions in microbial populations. Indeed, many studies have reported PEF-induced reductions more than 5.00 log CFU/ mL for different microorganisms.

3. Effects of PEF on the physicochemical characteristics.

Physicochemical parameters such as pH, titratable acidity, total soluble solids content and color are indicators used to evaluate the quality of fruit and vegetable juices. These characteristics have an intrinsic relationship with the sensory attributes perceived by the consumer. Therefore, processed juices that have properties close to fresh juice are more likely to be accepted by consumers. In this context, PEF technology has emerged as an alternative in the processing of natural juices, as it has the potential to preserve the physicochemical characteristics inherent to juices. In most

studies, PEF did not alter the physicochemical characteristics of fruit and vegetable juices even under conditions of high-energy application. In general, total soluble solids refer to substances dissolved in the aqueous phase of the evaluated sample. These substances include sugars, acids, phenolic compounds, pectins, vitamins, salts, among others [20,29]. In fruit and vegetable juices, the main solids present are carbohydrates such as sucrose, glucose, and fructose. Thus, the TSS in juices is associated with the carbohydrate content. This physicochemical property is related to the sensory attribute of sweetness in fruit and vegetable juices [30]. Several studies have indicated that PEF did not promote significant changes in TSS in fruit juices. [12,15,20]. Some studies reported an increase in TSS after processing with PEF [31]. Atencio et al. studied the effects of PEF (1.01 kV/cm, pulse width 80 μ s, 9 kJ/kg) on pumpkin juice and observed an increase in TSS from 2.54 to 2.80 °Brix. [31]. Buitimea Cantúa et al. applied PEF (11.3 to 23.3 kV/cm, pulse width 25 μ s, 100 pulses, 19.7 to 168.4 kJ/L) to raspberry juice. The results show an increase in TSS from 7.5 to 8.5 °Brix in all PEF treatments. [32]. As mentioned by Atencio et al. and Buitimea-Cantúa et al. the increase in total soluble solids occurs as a result of the release of carbohydrates from inside the cells into the aqueous medium of the juice, in addition to the action of enzymes responsible for producing these carbohydrates. However, some studies have observed a reduction in TSS values [33]. Ahmed et al. [33]. applied PEF (5 kV/cm, treatment time 20 min) to pineapple juice and observed a reduction in TSS from 12.06 to 11.03 °Brix. Wibowo et al. (2019) evaluated the effects of PEF treatment (12.5 kV/cm, pulse width 2 μ s, 62 and 94 Hz, 76.4 and 132.5 kJ/L) on cloudy apple juice, resulting in the least intense treatment of 76.4 kJ/L reducing the soluble solids content from 13.08 to 12.78 °Brix. Electroporation caused by PEF allows mass transfer across cell membranes. during the application of PEF, the soluble solids may have diffused into the intracellular environment, resulting in a reduction in the substances present in the aqueous phase. In this sense, before the application of PEF, the inside of the cells had a lower concentration of solids than the juice, thus resulting in the mass transfer of sugars from the juice to the inside of the cell structures present in the medium. This explanation was presented by Ahmed et al. to account for the reduction in TSS in pineapple juice treated with an electric field.

The organic acids present in fruits and derived products play an essential role in the perception of sour taste by consumers and in extending the shelf life of these foods. The main acids present in fruit and vegetable juices are citric acid, tartaric acid and malic acid. The concentration of acids in a product can be determined by titratable acidity. In several studies, PEF treatment has been shown to have no significant effects on TA [12,34]. The impact of PEF on the pH of fruit and vegetable juices is not consistently reported in research on the subject. Some studies have indicated that PEF treatment did not result in significant changes in pH [12,34]. Some studies have identified an increase in pH after PEF treatment [32,33]. However, the increase in pH implies a reduction in the concentration of ionic

hydrogen in the medium. This could result from the mass transfer of organic acids from the continuous phase into the cellular structure. The increased content of organic acids elevates the concentration of hydrogen ions, consequently lowering pH values. Buitimea-Cantúa et al. [32] investigating pH variations in raspberry juice resulting from PEF treatment (11.3 to 23.3 kV/cm, pulse width 25 μ s, 100 pulses, 19.7 to 168.4 kJ/L) at different frequencies (100, 200, and 500 Hz). All juice samples subjected to PEF treatment exhibited a higher pH than the untreated sample. Remarkably, treatments at frequencies of 100 Hz (19.7 and 79.7 kJ/L) and 500 Hz (113.8 kJ/L) resulted in the highest pH values. Concurrently with the pH increase, the results showed a reduction in TA. Therefore, the variations observed in pH and TA may be associated with the trapping of these substances in the raspberry cell matrix after electroporation caused by PEF. Sensors used for pH determination, for instance, quantify ions present in the aqueous medium. Therefore, when compounds migrate into the cell interior, fluctuations in the measured readings might be noticed. In this context, the application of PEF induces little or no significant change in the physicochemical characteristics of vegetable and fruit juices. The TSS, TA, and pH are quality parameters in the juice industry, and thus, preserving these properties is ideal when the goal is the development of a new process for the chemical and kinetic stabilization of products

Monitoring enzyme activity in fruit and vegetable juices is crucial when the aim is to preserve the sensory, nutritional and functional quality of the product for as long as possible. The main enzymes found in juices are polyphenol oxidase (PPO), peroxidase (POD) and pectin methyl esterase (PME). POD and PPO cause changes in the color of vegetable and fruit juices because of the oxidation of phenolic compounds, thus promoting the browning of the product. PME functions by de-esterifying the methoxyl groups of pectin, leading to the loss of cloud stability. Because of the reduced solubility of these polymers, fruit and vegetable juices experience a loss of cloud stability and phase separation in the product. Furthermore, the action of PME can alter other quality parameters of juices, such as viscosity, color, and flavor. Electric field processing is a viable alternative for quality control in terms of enzyme inactivation. Faisal Manzoor et al. [35] evaluated the enzymatic inactivation of PPO and POD in spinach juice treated with PEF (9 kV/cm, pulse width 80 μ s, treatment time 335 μ s, 1 kHz). The results indicated a reduction of 44.00% and 43.52% in PPO and POD activity, respectively. Ahmed et al. [26] applied PEF (9 kV/cm, pulse width 80 μ s, treatment time 335 μ s, 1 kHz) to wheat plant juice and assessed enzymatic activity, showing a reduction of 35.63% and 38.70% in the activity of POD and PPO enzymes, respectively. Regarding the effects of PEF on PME inactivation, Buitimea-Cantúa et al. [32] treated raspberry juice under conditions of 11.3 to 23.3 kV/cm, pulse width 25 μ s, 100 pulses, 19.7 to 168.4 kJ/L. The highest PME inhibition was observed in the treatment of 168.4 kJ/L, with a 19% activity inhibition, followed by treatments

of 79.7 and 113.8 kJ/L, both resulting in 13% inhibitions. Wibowo et al. [36] investigated the impacts of PEF (12.5 kV/cm, pulse width 2 μ s, 62 and 94 Hz, 76.4 and 132.5 kJ/L) on enzymes in cloudy apple juice. The PEF treatment with 76.4 kJ/L reduced approximately 36%, 49%, and 50% of PPO, POD, and PME activity, respectively, while the treatment with 132.5 kJ/L reduced the activity of both enzymes by over 90%. In this study, the juice temperature after PEF treatments was 60 °C and 73 °C for energy densities of 76.4 and 132.5 kJ/L, respectively. This study also compared PEF processing with thermal treatments TP1 (72 °C/15 s) and TP2 (85 °C/30 s). The reductions in the activity of enzymes POD, PPO, and PME were similar to the thermal treatments. Therefore, sample heating may have a synergistic effect when combined with PEF application concerning the reduction of activity in these enzymes. The mechanism of enzyme inactivation with PEF treatment has not yet been fully elucidated. Similar to the phenomenon of electroporation in the cell membrane, PEF causes a redistribution of charges in the enzyme structure. To conclude, although the mechanisms of enzymatic inactivation caused by PEF are not evident. Some studies have reported a reduction in the activity of deteriorating enzymes due to PEF treatment. Different enzymes, such as PPO, POD, and PME, showed varying levels of inactivation when the same process conditions were applied. Furthermore, increasing the intensity of the electric field treatment reduces enzymatic activity because higher energy levels induce more changes to the enzyme structure. In this context, the inactivation of PPO and POD preserves the nutritional and sensory qualities, preventing browning and flavor alterations in the juices. Simultaneously, the inactivation of PME by PEF contributes to greater cloud stability and reduced insoluble pectin, consequently minimizing the formation of precipitates in vegetable and fruit juices.

4. Effects of PEF on functional and nutritional properties.

Vegetables, fruits and derived products, such as juices, exhibit a variety of bioactive compounds produced due to cellular secondary metabolism, including phenolic compounds, proteins, lipids, terpenes, organic acids, carotenoids, polysaccharides, among others. Phenolic compounds are substances derived from the secondary metabolism of plants, thus forming a group of thousands of components. The main families of phenolic compounds are flavonoids, non-flavonoids (tannins, stilbenes, and lignans), and phenolic acids [37]. Phenolic compounds exhibit various beneficial nutraceutical effects for the human body, acting as antioxidants, anticancer agents, anti-inflammatory compounds, antidiabetics, and as prophylaxis for cardiovascular, neurological, and age-related diseases. Other factors, such as enzymatic reactions like the action of PPO polymerization with proteins, and excessively intense processing, can cause a reduction in the content of phenolic compounds in foods. Vegetable and fruit juices contain the phenolic compounds originally present in fruits. In addition to their high nutritional value, antioxidant activity, and various health benefits, phenolic compounds, specifically flavonoids and anthocyanins,

can contribute to the sensory characteristics of juices by enhancing the intensity of the final color of the product. These substances are pigments found in plants, fruits, and flowers, and they play a role in improving the color intensity of the final juice product [32]. Therefore, preserving phenolic compounds in juices during processing allows for the creation of juices that not only offer nutritional value but also contribute to health due to their nutraceutical effects. In this context, PEF technology emerges as a promising non-thermal technique for preserving the nutraceutical properties of vegetable and fruit juices by maintaining phenolic compounds. Several studies have observed that this technology does not modify the concentration of phenolic compounds in the juice samples treated with PEF [14,34]. The results obtained in these studies support the hypothesis that PEF is a promising alternative for juice processing without compromising beneficial phytochemical compounds for health. Some studies indicate an increase in the content of phenolic compounds present in the medium after applying PEF [26,32,35]. The results obtained in these studies may be associated with the phenomenon of electroporation, which enables the mobility of molecules through the cell membrane. Additionally, the increase in content of phenolic compounds is associated with an increase in antioxidant capacity, as observed in several studies [26,35]. Phenolic compounds exhibit antioxidant properties, thus, the release of these compounds into the aqueous medium enhances the antioxidant capacity of juice samples. However, certain studies have reported a decline in the level of phenolic compounds after PEF application [26,33]. The reduction in phenolic compounds might result from their degradation during processing. Sample heating due to the Joule effect could induce the degradation of these compounds. These substances are sensitive to temperature and can degrade under conditions of moderate and severe thermal treatment [36]. Other reasons for the reduction in the content of phenolic compounds include their oxidation due to the possible formation of free radicals during PEF processing and polymerization with proteins [33,38]. Jin et al. [24] investigated the impact of PEF treatment (19, 23, and 30 kV/cm, pulse width 2 μ s, treatment time 181 μ s, 1.25 kHz) on the phenolic content of apple juice. The results indicated that the PEF treatment at 19 kV/cm caused a decrease in the quantity of phenolic compounds, whereas the 23 kV/cm treatment showed no significant difference compared to the untreated sample. This outcome illustrates that process conditions directly influence the concentration of phenolic compounds in the juice. Furthermore, considering the effects of PEF on phenolic compounds and cellular membranes, the treatment at 19 kV/cm resulted in the degradation of phenolic compounds and a relatively insignificant release of intracellular content into the extracellular medium. Conversely, the treatment at 23 kV/cm degraded these substances and facilitated their diffusion into the extracellular medium through electroporation, thereby not significantly altering the content of phenolic compounds when compared to the untreated sample. The antioxidant effect of juices is related to the presence and concentration of phenolic compounds. Some studies

evaluated the antioxidant capacity after PEF application and reported an increase in this property [26,33,38]. Antioxidant compounds work to reduce free radicals, thus preventing oxidative stress in the human body. Reactions involving free radicals cause cellular alterations, damaging cell structures and compromising cellular function, resulting in oxidative stress. This stress can lead to the development of chronic diseases such as diabetes, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, among others [7,18,33,38]. Dziadek et al. [14]. and Oziembłowski et al. [39] evaluated phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity in apple and aronia juice treated with PEF (1st study – 30 kV/cm, 200 to 400 pulses, 0.033 Hz | 2nd study – 20 kV/cm, 300 pulses, pulse width 0.17 μ s, 0.066 Hz), respectively. The observed reduction in antioxidant activity was not linked to a decrease in content of phenolic compounds, as the concentrations of these substances showed no significant changes compared to the untreated sample. Therefore, other substances with antioxidant activity might have degraded during PEF processing. Given this, studies have reported that PEF technology does not alter the content of phenolic compounds. Moreover, there are studies that have shown an increase in the content of phenolic compounds because of the PEF technology application, which is associated with the electroporation phenomenon. Therefore, this innovative technology does not possess a severity level that compromises the content of these bioactive compounds present in vegetable and fruit juices.

Flavonoids constitute the most numerous groups of phenolic compounds. The subcategories of flavonoids include catechins, flavones, anthocyanidins, flavonols, flavanones, and isoflavones [40]. Anthocyanins are the primary flavonoids found in fruit and vegetable juices. As water-soluble pigments, they are primarily responsible for the blue, red, and purple coloration of these products. These pigments belong to the group of polyphenolic flavonoids and are considered part of the anthocyanidin family. They exhibit antioxidant capacity and are found in fruits, vegetables, and flowers [14,18,41]. In purified form, flavonoids and anthocyanins exhibit limited stability, primarily due to their susceptibility to nucleophilic attacks. Factors such as temperature, pH, the presence of metals, enzymes, oxygen, light, among others, affect the stability of anthocyanins [42,43]. Thermal processing-induced degradation depends on various variables such as the type of heating, duration, nature of the anthocyanins, and food matrix [43,44]. In this regard, PEF is a non-thermal technology that appears to be a promising alternative to meet this demand. Several studies have investigated the impact of PEF treatment on the content of flavonoids and anthocyanins in fruit and vegetable juices. Several studies have assessed the use of PEF technology in processing fruit and vegetable juices, observing the preservation of the content of these substances, resulting in the conservation of the nutraceutical properties in the beverage [33,43,44]. Furthermore, other studies present a beneficial effect of PEF on the concentration of these substances. Faisal Manzoor et al. [35] reported an increase of 5.81% and 8.23% in the content of flavonoids and anthocyanins after the application of PEF (9 kV/cm,

pulse width 80 μ s, treatment time 335 μ s, 1 kHz) in spinach juice. Rahaman et al. [43] investigated the effects of PEF (7 and 14 kV/cm, treatment time 500 μ s, 1 kHz) in apricot juice and observed an increase of 24.21 % and 83.32 % in the flavonoid content. Yildiz et al. [28] applied PEF (35 kV/cm, pulse width 2 μ s, 155 Hz, treatment time 27 μ s) to strawberry juice, evaluating the anthocyanin content. The results showed a 17.12% increase in the content of these substances. The increase in concentration of these substances represents an enhancement in the functional and nutraceutical properties of the juices. Additionally, alterations in the anthocyanin content might influence the color of the beverage compared to the untreated sample. Faisal Manzoor et al. [35] also evaluated the color parameters of spinach juice after the PEF treatment. The values of “L”, “a”, “hue (saturation)”, and “chroma” were altered by the electric field treatment compared to the untreated sample. The pores generated by PEF enable the diffusion of substances from the intracellular to the extracellular environment. Consequently, flavonoids and anthocyanins present within plant cells become available in the juice, resulting in color changes. In summary, although anthocyanins and flavonoids are substances sensitive to oxygen, light, high temperatures, and other factors, the application of PEF did not compromise the content of these substances in fruit and vegetable juices, as reported in the studies. Thus, the bioactive properties and sensory characteristics, such as color, are preserved in juices treated with the electric field [43,44].

5. Prospects and problems of PEF application in juice production

The PEF processing is a non-thermal and innovative technology based on electroporation, which can be applied for microbial and enzymatic inactivation, recovery, and preservation of bioactive compounds and pigments, among others. Therefore, PEF-based processes in vegetable and fruit juices are an alternative to thermal processes employed for stabilization, as this technology can result in kinetically and chemically stable products without compromising bioactive compounds and sensory characteristics, as presented in this review. Pasteurization is the most used thermal process in the processing of vegetable and fruit juices, which not only alters the physicochemical characteristics and content of bioactive compounds but also compromises nutritional quality, promoting changes in the sensory characteristics of the products. In this context, PEF technology emerges as an alternative to pasteurization in the juice industry. For the application of the PEF in the juice industry, studies should be conducted to determine efficient process variables concerning technical and economic viability. For instance, the set of applied variables, such as field strength, frequency, pulse width, and total treatment duration, should ensure complete inactivation of the target microorganism for each specific product, and reduce the activity of deteriorating enzymes. Economically, the PEF application should offset the costs of installation, maintenance, and energy consumption of this technology, allowing large-scale production. Additionally, the price must be affordable for the consumer. The PEF technology emerges as a non-thermal food processing alternative.

However, there are several gaps that need to be studied, explored, and elucidated. For instance, it is crucial to comprehend mechanisms related to enzymatic and microbial inactivation, as well as intracellular compound extraction, among other factors. In the specific context of vegetable and fruit juices, applying PEF to achieve safe and kinetically and chemically stable products demands a detailed analysis of key process variables. These variables encompass the field strength (kV/cm), frequency (Hz), pulse width (μ s), number of pulses, total treatment duration, and other factors that significantly impact the characteristics of the final product. Additionally, comprehending the complex interactions between the intrinsic features of raw materials and process conditions is essential. In the context of vegetable and fruit juices, applying PEF to obtain stable products needs to be studied to determine the main process variables (field strength, frequency, pulse width, total treatment duration, among others) that impact the final product characteristics. Furthermore, understanding the interactions between the intrinsic characteristics of raw materials and process conditions becomes necessary. The information presented previously is primary for implementing PEF technology in vegetable and fruit juice processing into an industrial scale, providing not only safety and chemical/kinetic stability to products but also data for advancing the development of this non-thermal food processing alternative.

6. Conclusion

The PEF technology is a promising alternative for processing vegetable and fruit juices. In this review, the potential of PEF in reducing microbial load and undesirable enzymatic activity without significant impacts on the physicochemical and sensory characteristics of the products was examined. Additionally, an increase in the availability of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and anthocyanins, substances with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer properties, preventing chronic diseases, and contributing to the appearance of the juices, was observed. Some application conditions of PEF have proven that the technology has a low severity level by degrading little or preserving ascorbic acid. However, future studies on the application of PEF technology are necessary. Issues related to microbial and enzymatic inactivation, obtaining intracellular compounds, and other aspects need to be investigated more deeply. There are also recommendations for studies on PEF process design with low severity, aiming for effective chemical, microbiological, and kinetic stabilization of vegetable and fruit juices.

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